

AREAS AND STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF A COMMUNICATION
OPERATOR

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Abstract. In this article, the author comments on the current state of the service industry and the role and importance of communication services in it. In addition, the analysis of data on the service mechanisms of communication operators, the role of communication services in the world market is presented.

Key words: service, communication services, mobile communication, Internet services.

Human society cannot be imagined without information. With the help of information, the activities of society members and its constituent units are managed, future plans are defined, their implementation is monitored and analyzed. The spiritual, educational, cultural and other requirements of the members of the uninformed society remain unsatisfied. Therefore, meeting the need for information is one of the priority goals of any human society. Achieving this priority goal makes continuous development of the field of communication services an objective necessity in any human society. The development of this sector is one of the most important factors in ensuring the socio-economic development of any country.

In the world, the field of communication is recognized as an important "locomotive" of socio-economic development. According to the sources, "50% of the productivity gains in the member states of the Council of Europe are achieved through communication; a 10% increase in investment in Internet services leads to an increase in gross domestic product (GDP) by 1-2%; By the beginning of 2020, more than 4.5 billion people worldwide use the Internet, more than 3.8 billion people access social networks, more than 5.19 billion people have mobile phones;

53% of Internet accesses are made through mobile phones, 44% through personal computers; 64% of Britons do their shopping online via mobile.

Telecommunications infrastructure is the basis for the development of information and telecommunication technologies (ICT). Digitization of telecommunication networks in Uzbekistan has fully covered the territory of the country. The generation of modern electronic telephone exchanges of NGN and MPLS type is used in this network. The numbered capacity of wired communication networks is over a million. In the territory of Uzbekistan, every citizen and institution has the opportunity to install wired telephones.

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The field of communication services is a structural division of the economy that has its own characteristics and differs from other sectors in various aspects. These specific features and different aspects are clearly manifested in the content and essence of the types of communication services, in the technique and technology of their presentation, in the types of products being created, in their formalization with relevant documents, and other aspects. Features and differences in these and other aspects, on the one hand, the emergence of new types of services from day to day makes it an objective necessity to conduct a deep study of the existing problems and, on this basis, to scientifically justify the ways to solve them.

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